

MINIMUM COST DESIGN OF A HYBRID LAMINATE WITH UNCERTAIN MATERIAL PROPERTIES SUBJECT TO FREQUENCY CONSTRAINTS

Isaac S. Radebe¹ and Sarp Adali²

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Durban University of Technology
Durban 4000, South Africa, email: sfisor@dut.ac.za

²Discipline of Mechanical Engineering, University of KwaZulu-Natal
Durban 4041, South Africa, email: adali@ukzn.ac.za

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ABSTRACT

Minimum cost design of hybrid cross-ply laminates is presented which employ the expensive materials such as carbon fibre reinforced plastics in the upper layers and the inexpensive material such as glass fibre reinforced plastics in the middle layers. The design is obtained for a given vibration frequency. Hybrid construction takes advantage of the sandwich effect whereby most of the load is carried by the surface layers. The laminate has material properties which are not known deterministically, but only with some level of uncertainty. The model employed in the present research is uncertain-but-bounded variations around the nominal values of the elastic constants. For a given frequency, the minimum possible thickness of the expensive layers is determined. Analysis to determine the worst-case combination of material uncertainties makes use of convex modeling to compute the least favorable solution defined here as the smallest frequency. The minimum cost designs are investigated for different levels of uncertainty.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hybrid constructions can be used effectively to reduce the material costs by using more expensive materials in the outer layers and less expensive materials in the inner layers. A typical case is the use of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) in the outer layers and Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics (GFRP) in the inner layers. The cost of the component can be further reduced by minimizing the thickness of the outer layers. Previous studies on the optimization of hybrid laminates include Abachizadeh and Tahani (2009), Adali and Duffy (1992, 1993), Adali et al. (1995), Adali and Verijenko (1997, 2001) and Aiello and Ombres (1996, 2007).

Noting that variations in the elastic constants of composite materials are not unusual, the design can take the variations in material properties into account. In such situations material properties can be treated as uncertain variables. For a robust design, the computations can be based on the “worst-case” of material properties. Information on the bounds on elastic constants could be available leading to bounded-but-uncertain properties. In such cases the problem can be analyzed using convex models of uncertainty. By taking the variations about the average values of the uncertain variables, the least favorable solution (worst-case) can be computed and a conservative design can be obtained. This approach contrasts with a deterministic analysis where the average values of elastic constants are employed in the calculations. Recent studies on the application of convex analysis to structural problems include Hu and Qiu (2010), Kang et al. (2011), Qiu (2005), Qui et al. (2009) and Radebe and Adali (2014).

In the present study, the thickness of the outer layers of a hybrid cross-ply laminate is determined for a given frequency with the material properties taken as uncertain. As the uncertainties only involve

the elastic constants, the material remains orthotropic after the uncertainties are implemented. The laminate consists of three layers with the outer layers made of a composite with high modulus fiber and the middle layer of a composite with low modulus fibers. The minimum cost design is achieved by using the minimum amount of the high modulus fibers for a given design frequency.

2. HYBRID CROSS-PLY LAMINATE

The cross-ply hybrid laminate under consideration consists of three layers with fibre orientations of 0° or 90° with different composite materials in the top and middle layers. The material of the outer layers is normally a high modulus composite such as carbon or boron FRP and the material for the middle (inner) layer is of a low modulus composite such as glass FRP. The rectangular laminate has dimensions of a and b in the x and y directions and thickness h in the z direction. The equation governing the vibration of the of a cross-ply laminate can be expressed as

$$\tilde{D}_{11} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2(\tilde{D}_{12} + 2\tilde{D}_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \tilde{D}_{22} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} + \rho_{hyb} h \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

In eq. (1), ρ_{hyb} is the mass density of the hybrid laminate and \tilde{D}_{ij} ($i, j=1,2,6$) are the bending stiffness coefficients where the overhead \sim sign indicates an uncertain quantity. Let the composite material in the outer layers be identified by subscript A and that of the middle layer by subscript B . Then the stiffness coefficients \tilde{D}_{ij} can be expressed as

$$\tilde{D}_{ij} = \tilde{D}_{ijA} + \tilde{D}_{ijB} \quad (2)$$

with \tilde{D}_{ijA} and \tilde{D}_{ijB} given by

$$\tilde{D}_{ijA} = H_A(\alpha) \tilde{Q}_{ijA}, \quad \tilde{D}_{ijB} = H_B(\alpha) \tilde{Q}_{ijB} \quad (3)$$

where α is the hybridization parameter such that the total thickness of the outer layers is given by $t_A = \alpha h$ and the thickness of the middle layer is given $t_B = (1 - \alpha)h$. In eq. (3), H_A and H_B are given by

$$H_A = \frac{h^3}{12} (1 - (1 - \alpha)^3), \quad H_B = \frac{h^3}{12} (1 - \alpha)^3 \quad (4)$$

Let the subscript $p = A$ or B denote the material A (outer layers) and material B (middle layer). The transformed stiffnesses \tilde{Q}_{ijp} are given by

$$\tilde{Q}_{11p} = \tilde{Q}_{11p} \cos^4 \theta_p + \tilde{Q}_{22p} \sin^4 \theta_p, \quad \tilde{Q}_{12p} = \tilde{Q}_{12p} \quad (5a)$$

$$\tilde{Q}_{22p} = \tilde{Q}_{11p} \sin^4 \theta_p + \tilde{Q}_{22p} \cos^4 \theta_p, \quad \tilde{Q}_{66p} = \tilde{Q}_{66p} \quad (5b)$$

where $\theta_p = 0^\circ$ or 90° and

$$\tilde{Q}_{11p} = \frac{\tilde{E}_{11p}}{\Delta_p}, \quad \tilde{Q}_{12p} = \frac{\nu_{12p} \tilde{E}_{22p}}{\Delta_p}, \quad \tilde{Q}_{22p} = \frac{\tilde{E}_{22p}}{\Delta_p}, \quad \tilde{Q}_{66p} = \tilde{G}_{12p}, \quad \Delta_p = 1 - \nu_{12p} \nu_{21p} \quad (6)$$

In eq. (6), \tilde{E}_{11p} , \tilde{E}_{22p} are uncertain Young's moduli in the material directions, \tilde{G}_{12p} is the uncertain shear modulus, and ν_{12p} is ν_{21p} are in-plane Poisson's ratios. For a simply supported plate the solution is given by

$$w(x, y) = C_{mn} \sin \alpha_m x \sin \beta_n y e^{i\omega t} \quad (7)$$

where $\alpha_m = m\pi/a$ and $\beta_n = n\pi/b$. Substituting eq. (7) into the equation of motion (1), the frequencies are computed as

$$\omega_{mn}^2 = \frac{1}{\rho_{hyb} h} \left[\tilde{D}_{11} \alpha_m^4 + 2(\tilde{D}_{12} + 2\tilde{D}_{66}) \alpha_m^2 \beta_n^2 + \tilde{D}_{22} \beta_n^4 \right] \quad (8)$$

for symmetrically laminated cross-ply plates.

3. UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS

In the present section, a first order uncertainty analysis is implemented to express the frequency in terms of the material variations. For this purpose, uncertain elastic constants are defined as

$$\tilde{E}_{11p} = E_{11p}^0 (1 + \delta_{1p}), \quad \tilde{E}_{22p} = E_{22p}^0 (1 + \delta_{2p}), \quad \tilde{G}_{12p} = G_{12p}^0 (1 + \delta_{3p}) \quad (9)$$

where $p = A$ or B , and the superscript "0" denotes the nominal values of the elastic constants. The constants δ_{ip} represent the unknown variations of the elastic constants, can be positive or negative and satisfy the inequalities $|\delta_{ip}| \ll 1$. They are determined by convex analysis to yield the least favorable frequencies leading to a robust design. Substituting eqs. (9) into eqs. (5), we obtain

$$\tilde{Q}_{11p} = \frac{E_{11p}^0}{\Delta_p} \cos^4 \theta_p (1 + \delta_{1p}) + \frac{E_{22p}^0}{\Delta_p} \sin^4 \theta_p (1 + \delta_{2p}), \quad \tilde{Q}_{12p} = \frac{\nu_{12p} E_{22p}^0}{\Delta_p} (1 + \delta_{2p}) \quad (10a)$$

$$\tilde{Q}_{22p} = \frac{E_{11p}^0}{\Delta_p} \sin^4 \theta_p (1 + \delta_{1p}) + \frac{E_{22p}^0}{\Delta_p} \cos^4 \theta_p (1 + \delta_{2p}), \quad \tilde{Q}_{66p} = G_{12p}^0 (1 + \delta_{3k}) \quad (10b)$$

The frequencies can be expressed in terms of the variations of the uncertain elastic constants by

$$\omega_{mn}^2(\delta_{ip}) = \frac{1}{\rho_{hyb} h} \left[\begin{aligned} &H_A(\alpha) \left(\tilde{Q}_{11A} + 2(\tilde{Q}_{12A} + 2\tilde{Q}_{66A}) \alpha_m^2 \beta_n^2 + \tilde{Q}_{22A} \beta_n^4 \right) \\ &+ H_B(\alpha) \left(\tilde{Q}_{11B} + 2(\tilde{Q}_{12B} + 2\tilde{Q}_{66B}) \alpha_m^2 \beta_n^2 + \tilde{Q}_{22B} \beta_n^4 \right) \end{aligned} \right] \quad (11)$$

where \tilde{Q}_{ijp} terms are given by eqs. (10). Thus the frequencies can be expressed as

$$\lambda_{mn}(\delta_{ip}) = \frac{1}{\rho_{hyb} h} \left[g_{0A} + g_{0B} + \sum_1^3 g_{iA} \delta_{iA} + \sum_1^3 g_{iB} \delta_{iB} \right] \quad (12)$$

where $\lambda_{mn}(\delta_i) = \omega_{mn}^2(\delta_i)$ and the terms g_{ip} are obtained by substituting eq. (10) into eq. (11).

4. CONVEX ANALYSIS

In this section the least favorable frequencies corresponding to the worst-case distribution of the uncertainties is computed by convex analysis. For this purpose we introduce constraints on the variations δ_{ip} in the form of ellipsoids, viz.

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 \delta_{ip}^2 \leq \gamma_p^2, \quad p = A, B \quad (13)$$

where $\gamma_p < 1$ determines the level of uncertainty for the elastic constants of Material A and material B and $\gamma_p = 0$ corresponds to the deterministic case. It is observed that the level of uncertainty could be different for composites used in the outer and middle layers. The frequencies λ_{mn} depend on the level of uncertainty as measured by γ_p and a higher γ_p leads to a smaller frequencies as expected. The expression (12) for λ_{mn} has to be minimized with respect to the constants δ_{ip} and subject to the constraints (13) to determine the lowest frequencies for given levels of uncertainty. For this purpose, a Lagrangian is formulated noting that the constraints given by eq. (13) yield the lowest frequencies when the δ_{ip} values lie on the surface of the ellipsoid, i.e., when $\sum_{i=1}^3 \delta_{ip}^2 - \gamma_p^2 = 0$. Thus the

Lagrangian takes the following form

$$L(g_{ip}, \delta_{ip}) = \frac{1}{\rho_{hyb} h} \left(g_{0A} + g_{0B} + \sum_1^3 g_{iA} \delta_{iA} + \sum_1^3 g_{iB} \delta_{iB} \right) + \mu_A \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 \delta_{iA}^2 - \gamma_A^2 \right) + \mu_B \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 \delta_{iB}^2 - \gamma_B^2 \right) \quad (14)$$

where μ_A and μ_B are Lagrange multipliers. The minima and the maxima of the Lagrangian are determined from

$$\frac{\partial L(g_{ip}, \delta_{ip})}{\partial \delta_{ip}} = 0 \quad (15)$$

The parameters δ_{ip} are computed from eq. (15) as

$$\delta_{iA} = -\frac{1}{2\rho_{hyb} h} \frac{g_{iA}}{\mu_A}, \quad \delta_{iB} = -\frac{1}{2\rho_{hyb} h} \frac{g_{iB}}{\mu_B} \quad (16)$$

The Lagrange multipliers μ_A and μ_B are computed from $\sum_{i=1}^3 \delta_{ip}^2 - \gamma_p^2 = 0$ as

$$\mu_A = \pm \frac{1}{2\rho_{hyb} h \gamma_A} \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 g_{iA}^2 \right)^{1/2}, \quad \mu_B = \pm \frac{1}{2\rho_{hyb} h \gamma_B} \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 g_{iB}^2 \right)^{1/2} \quad (17)$$

Thus

$$\delta_{iA} = \mp \gamma_A g_{iA} \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 g_{iA}^2 \right)^{-1/2}, \quad \delta_{iB} = \mp \gamma_B g_{iB} \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 g_{iB}^2 \right)^{-1/2} \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (18)$$

where the plus and minus signs correspond to the lowest and highest frequencies.

5. MINIMUM COST DESIGN

The minimum cost design refers to a hybrid design where a minimum amount of the expensive fibers such as carbon or boron is used in the outer layers for a given frequency, thereby keeping the cost at the minimum level possible. The hybridization parameter α denotes ratio of the thickness t_A of the layer made of a high modulus composite to the wall thickness h of the cylinder, i.e.,

$$\alpha = \frac{t_A}{h} \quad (19)$$

The minimum cost is achieved by minimizing α for a given value of the frequency $\lambda_{11}(\alpha, \gamma_A, \gamma_B)$. Moreover the constraint $\sum_{i=1}^3 \delta_{ik}^2 - \gamma_k^2 = 0$ on the material variations has to be satisfied.

6. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The effect of material uncertainty on the frequencies is studied by specifying the high modulus composite as CFRP (Material *A*) and the low modulus composite as GFRP (Material *B*). The nominal values of the elastic constants and density of CFRP are taken as

$$E_{11}^0 = 181.0 \text{ GPa}, E_{22}^0 = 10.3 \text{ GPa}, G_{12}^0 = 7.17 \text{ GPa}, \nu_{12} = 0.28, \rho_c = 1600 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

and for GFRP as

$$E_{11}^0 = 38.6 \text{ GPa}, E_{22}^0 = 8.27 \text{ GPa}, G_{12}^0 = 4.14 \text{ GPa}, \nu_{12} = 0.26, \rho_g = 1800 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

The density of the hybrid composite is given by $\rho_{hyb} = \alpha\rho_c + (1-\alpha)\rho_g$. The frequency is normalized by

$$\Omega_{mn} = \frac{\rho_0}{h^2 E_0} \lambda_{mn} \quad (20)$$

where $\rho_0 = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $E_0 = 1 \text{ GPa}$. The results are given for a square plate. Note that $\gamma = 0$ indicates the deterministic case and $\gamma > 0$ the uncertain case. The fibre orientations θ_c and θ_g refer to the ply angles of the CFRP layers and GFRP layers, respectively.

Figure 1: Frequencies vs the hybridization parameter α for $\gamma = 0$, $\theta_c = \theta_g = 0^\circ$

Figure 1 shows Ω_{mn} with respect to α for different m and n values for the deterministic case for $\theta_c = \theta_g = 0^\circ$. The corresponding results for $\gamma = 0.3$ are given in Figure 2 which indicates the decrease in the frequencies due to the uncertainty in material properties. The thickness $t_c = \alpha h$ of the CFRP layers can be determined from these graphs for a given value of Ω_{mn} .

Figure 2: Frequencies vs the hybridization parameter α for $\gamma = 0.3$, $\theta_c = \theta_g = 0^\circ$

Figure 3. Contour plot of Ω_{11} with respect to α and γ for $\theta_c = \theta_g = 0^\circ$

Contour plot of Ω_{11} with respect to γ ($0 \leq \gamma \leq 0.3$) and α is shown in Figure 3 for $\theta_c = \theta_g = 0^\circ$. The thickness $t_c = \alpha h$ of CFRP can be determined from Figure 3 for a given value of Ω_{11} and the level of uncertainty γ .

Figure 4: Curves of frequency for $m = 2, n = 1$ vs the hybridization parameter α for $\gamma = 0$

Figure 4 shows Ω_{21} with respect to α for different combinations of fibre orientations for the deterministic case ($\gamma = 0$). The highest frequency is obtained for $\theta_c = \theta_g = 0^\circ$. The corresponding results for $\gamma = 0.3$ are given in Figure 5 which indicates the decrease in the frequencies due to the uncertainty in material properties.

Figure 5: Curves of frequency vs the hybridization parameter α for $\gamma = 0.3$

9. CONCLUSIONS

Minimum cost design problem was studied for hybrid cross-ply laminates consisting of high-stiffness upper layers and a low-stiffness middle layer with the material properties exhibiting variations around their nominal values. Minimum cost designs are obtained by minimizing the

thickness of the expensive layers for a given frequency and uncertainty level with the elastic constants determined to produce the lowest frequencies.

The numerical results were given for graphite-epoxy/glass-epoxy laminates. The effects of the level of uncertainty, different combinations of ply angles and the thickness of the upper layers on the frequencies were studied and the increase in the uncertainty was shown to lead to a decrease in the frequencies.

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